

INDIA'S MERCHANDISE TRADE WITH CHINA

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Abstract

Objective- India and China are the two countries of Asia with huge population, market size and growth opportunities. In 1984, India and China signed the Most Favored Nation (MFN) agreement. In 1994, India and China signed an agreement to avoid double taxation with respect to income tax. Objective of the paper is to analyze the growth of India's merchandise trade with China. Secondary objective is to identify the composition of India's merchandise trade with China.

Design / Methodology/ Approach- The present research paper is comparative analysis of India's merchandise trade with China. This research paper is based on secondary data, taken from website of Department of Commerce, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India.

Findings- From 2000 to 2015, value of export from India to China has increased almost 20 times and value of Import from China to India has increased almost 54 times. India exports mainly primary commodities to China and imports secondary commodities from China.

Limitations- This research paper is mainly based on secondary data only, taken from website of Department of Commerce, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India.

Practical implications- This research paper will be helpful to those who are interested in India and China trade relations.

Originality/Value- This research paper will be a base for future researches on similar topics.

Key words: Merchandise, Trade, Export, Import.

INTRODUCTION:

Trade is selling or purchasing of goods or services in exchange of goods, money or services. In trade, the ownership of goods transfers from one person or entity to another. Trade has economic, political and social importance for any country.

Trade can be divided into domestic trade and international trade. When trade is done between two or more countries it is called international trade or foreign trade. In recent decade's foreign trade have increased mainly because of rapid development in Industrialization, advanced communication and transportation system, globalization and outsourcing. When trader of a country sells goods to another country it is called export. On the other side when a country purchases goods from another country it is called import. For example when India sell product to China it becomes export of India and import for China.

Foreign trade is an engine of economic growth of a country. The progress of a country largely depends to the extent on the ability to trade with the rest of the world. World's larger population lives in Asia. India and China are the two major countries of Asia with huge population, market size, and growth opportunities. India and China have increased their global market share in terms of trade.

To build better trade relation and cooperation between each other, India and China have signed a trade agreement in 1984. In 1994, India and China signed an agreement for the avoidance of double taxation with respect to income tax. China acceded for Asia-Pacific Trade Agreement (APTA), previously known as the Bangkok Agreement. The aim of A.P.T.A is to promote economic development and cooperation through the adoption of mutually beneficial trade liberalization measures. India is original member of A.P.T.A.

In 2000-01, China was India's twelfth largest trading partner, as its share being only 2.45% in India's total foreign trade. But It rose to 4.18% in 2003-04 (stood at 5th position) and substantially rise to 7.57% in 2005-06 (stood at 3rd position). In 2009-10, China become largest trading partner of India with share of 9.26 % in India's total foreign trade.

Merchandise trade includes trade in goods only and it does not take in consideration, trade in services, capital transfers and foreign investments. In other words we can say that merchandise trade is trade of physical goods only. This research paper is an comparative analysis of India's merchandise trade with China.

OBJECTIVE:

- To do comparative analysis of India's merchandise trade with China since 2000-01.
- To identify the composition of India's merchandise trade with China.

Table-1

India's Merchandise Trade with China						
Amount in Rs Crore						
Year	Export (Rs)	Growth %	Import (Rs)	Growth %	Total Trade (Rs)	Trade Balance (Rs)
2000-2001	3,797.76	-	6,862.70	-	10,660.45	-3,064.94
2001-2002	4,540.04	19.55	9,711.92	33.69	14,251.96	-5,171.89
2002-2003	9,560.39	110.58	13,512.15	61.89	23,072.54	-3,951.76
2003-2004	13,579.06	42.03	18,625.14	39.58	32,204.20	-5,046.08
2004-2005	25,232.97	85.82	31,892.31	77.38	57,125.28	-6,659.34
2005-2006	29,924.91	18.59	48,116.65	36.61	78,041.57	-18,191.74
2006-2007	37,529.78	25.41	79,008.61	49.33	116,538.39	-41,478.83
2007-2008	43,597.42	16.17	109,116.07	31.04	152,713.49	-65,518.66
2008-2009	42,661.33	-2.15	147,605.60	24.59	190,266.93	-104,944.26
2009-2010	54,713.93	28.25	146,048.61	5.52	200,762.54	-91,334.68
2010-2011	64,315.14	17.55	198,079.08	30.70	262,394.22	-133,763.93
2011-2012	87,470.82	36.00	265,465.62	34.51	352,936.44	-177,994.80
2012-2013	73,529.56	-15.94	284,384.59	1.41	357,914.15	-210,855.02
2013-2014	90,561.09	23.16	309,234.96	11.70	399,796.05	-218,673.87
2014-2015	73,030.43	-19.36	369,565.36	10.71	442,595.79	-296,534.93

Source: Calculations based on the data from website <http://commerce.nic.in/eidb/default.asp>

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

- In order to meet the desired objectives secondary data is taken from website of Department of Commerce, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India.
- The study period is from year 2000 to 2015.
- For better analysis and comparison, year 2008 is taken as mid point of the study period.
- Value of import and export is taken in Indian Rupees as given in website.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION: Table-1 shows the year wise detail of export, import their growth rate in percentage, total trade and trade balance of India with China.

India's merchandise export to China: The following bar graph indicates India's merchandise export to china. The description of figure-1 is given in table-2 below the graph.

Figure-1

Table-2

Opening year of Study period	2000-2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> India's merchandise export to China is Rs 3,797.76 crore
Mid year of Study period	2007-2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value of India's merchandise export to China is Rs 43,597.42 crore, which is approximately 12 times more than the value of 2000-01 i.e. Rs 3,797.76. This is a fabulous progress in the value of India's merchandise export to China.
Final year of study period	2014-2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> India's export to China becomes Rs 73,030.43 crore, which is approximately 2 times more than the value of 2007-08 i.e. Rs 43,597.42 crore and approximately 20 times more than the value of 2000-01 i.e. Rs 3,797.76 crore. This shows that there is tremendous progress in the value of India's merchandise export to China since 2000-01. There is wide fluctuations in the growth rate of India's merchandise export to China and is varying from 110.58% to -19.36%. There is a positive trend in the growth rate except in the years 2008-2009, 2012-2013 and 2014-2015. Finally we can say that although there is positive trend in growth rate of India's merchandise export to China but because of wide fluctuation in growth rate it is not considered to be good.

India's merchandise import from China: The following figure-2, bar graph shows India's merchandise import from China. The description of this figure is given in tabular form in table-3 below the graph.

Figure-2

Table 3

Opening year of Study period	2000-2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> India's merchandise import from China is Rs 6,862.70 crore
Mid year of Study period	2007-2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value of India's merchandise import from China is Rs 1,09,116.07 crore which is approximately 16 times more than the value of 2000-01 i.e. Rs 6,862.70 crore This is huge growth in the value of India's merchandise import from China.
Final year of study period	2014-2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> India's import from China become Rs 3,69,565.36 crore which is approximately 4 times more than the value of 2007-08 i.e. Rs

		<p>1,09,116.07 crore and 54 times more than the value of 2000-01 i.e. Rs 6,862.70 crore</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This shows that there is huge growth in the value of India's merchandise import from China since 2000-01. • There is wide fluctuations in the growth rate of India's merchandise import from China and is varying from 77.38% to 1.41%. • There is a positive trend in the growth rate in all the years of study period and not even a single year has shown negative growth. • Finally we can say that this growth in import is indicator of healthy trade relations of India and China.
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Comparative analysis of India-China export and import:

Figure-3

Table-4

Opening year of Study period	2000-01	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • India's export to China is Rs 3,797.76 crore and India's import from China is Rs 6,862.70 crore. • India's import is almost double than export. As a result Trade balance is Rs -3,064.94 crore, which is India's trade imbalance in favour of China.
Mid year of Study period	2007-08	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • India's export to China becomes Rs 43,597.42 crore, which is approximately 12 times more than the value of 2000-01. • India's import from China was Rs 1,09,116.07 crore which is approximately 16 times more than the value of 2000-01. • India's import is approximately 3 times more than export.
Final year of study period	2014-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • India's export to China is Rs 73,030.43 crore, which is approximately 20 times more as it was in 2000-01 and approximately 2 times more than the value of 2007-08. • India's import from China is Rs 3,69,565.36 crore which is approximately 54 times more than the value of 2000-01. • India's import is 5 times more than export. • Finally it is observed that India is continuously importing more than exporting to China. Difference between import and export is also widening year by year.

Trade balance between India and China:

Figure-4

Table-5

Opening year of study period	2000-2001	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> India's merchandise export to China was Rs 3,797.76 crore and India's merchandise import from China was Rs 6,862.70 crore, so trade balance was Rs -3,064.94 crore. It is India's trade imbalance heavily in favour of China.
Mid year of study period	2007-2008	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> India's merchandise export to China is Rs 43,597.42 crore, and India's merchandise import from China was Rs 1,09,116.07 crore, so trade balance is Rs -65,518.66 crore which is approximately 22 times more than the value of 2000-01 i.e. Rs -3,064.94 crore. This is again India's trade imbalance in favour of China.
Final year of study period	2014-2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> India's merchandise export to China is Rs 73,030.43 crore and India's merchandise import

		from China was Rs 3,69,565.36 crore, so trade balance is Rs -2,96,534.93 crore which is approximately 5 times more than the value of 2007-08 and approximately 97 times more than the value of 2000-01.
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The above graph and table reveals that, trade balance between India and China was not ever in favor of India and showing continuously negative balance since 2000-01. The difference between import and export keep on increasing year by year in the study period. This shows India is importing much more than its export to China.

Composition of foreign trade:

Composition of foreign trade means composition of commodities in import and export of a particular country. An analysis of composition of trade helps us to understand about the economic condition and progress of that country. For example if a country mainly exports primary commodities like tea, jute, cotton, iron ores etc and imports capital equipment and machinery, finished goods, etc it indicates that the particular country is in the stage of an underdeveloped economy, as it mainly exporting labor intensive goods and importing capital intensive goods. On the other hand if a particular country exports Machinery, components of airplanes, computers then it indicates that country has reached a high level of economic development, as it is exporting capital intensive goods.

India's Merchandise Trade with China: Composition of Import

Table-6
Top Commodities Imported from China in 2000-01

S.No	Product [H.S. code 2-Digit]	Amount in Rs Crore	Percentage (%) of India's total import from China
1	MINERAL FUELS, MINERAL OILS AND PRODUCTS OF THEIR DISTILLATION; BITUMINOUS SUBSTANCES; MINERAL WAXES.	1,202.71	17.53 %
2	ORGANIC CHEMICALS	1,138.84	16.59 %
3	NUCLEAR REACTORS, BOILERS, MACHINERY AND MECHANICAL APPLIANCES; PARTS THEREOF.	861.93	12.56 %
4	ELECTRICAL MACHINERY AND EQUIPMENT AND PARTS THEREOF; SOUND RECORDERS AND REPRODUCERS, TELEVISION IMAGE AND SOUND RECORDERS AND REPRODUCERS, AND PARTS.	737.57	10.75 %
5	SILK	517.78	7.54 %
6	SALT; SULPHUR; EARTHS AND STONE; PLASTERING MATERIALS, LIME AND CEMENT.	376.55	5.49 %
7	INORGANIC CHEMICALS; ORGANIC OR INORGANIC COMPOUNDS OF PRECIOUS METALS, OF RARE-EARTH METALS, OR RAD. ELEM. OR OF ISOTOPES.	231.53	3.37 %
8	NATURAL OR CULTURED PEARLS, PRECIOUS OR SEMIPRECIOUS STONES, PRE. METALS, CLAD WITH PRE. METAL AND ARTCLS THEREOF; IMIT. JEWELRY; COIN.	123.70	1.80 %
9	ZINC AND ARTICLES THEREOF.	106.37	1.55 %
10	OPTICAL, PHOTOGRAPHIC CINEMATOGRAPHIC MEASURING, CHECKING PRECISION, MEDICAL OR SURGICAL INST. AND APPARATUS PARTS AND ACCESSORIES THEREOF.	92.66	1.35 %
	INDIA'S TOTAL	6,862.70	

Source: Calculations based on the data from website <http://commerce.nic.in/eidb/default.asp>

Table-7

Top Commodities Imported from China in 2007-08			
S.No	Product [H.S. code 2-Digit]	Amount in Rs Crore	Percentage (%) of India's total import from China
1	ELECTRICAL MACHINERY AND EQUIPMENT AND PARTS THEREOF; SOUND RECORDERS AND REPRODUCERS, TELEVISION IMAGE AND SOUND RECORDERS AND REPRODUCERS, AND PARTS.	30,699.73	28.13 %
2	NUCLEAR REACTORS, BOILERS, MACHINERY AND MECHANICAL APPLIANCES; PARTS THEREOF.	19,413.73	17.79 %
3	ORGANIC CHEMICALS	9,590.05	8.79 %
4	IRON AND STEEL	5,876.79	5.39 %
5	MINERAL FUELS, MINERAL OILS AND PRODUCTS OF THEIR DISTILLATION; BITUMINOUS SUBSTANCES; MINERAL WAXES.	5,218.12	4.78 %
6	FERTILISERS.	4,716.07	4.32 %
7	ARTICLES OF IRON OR STEEL	4,639.55	4.25 %
8	PLASTIC AND ARTICLES THEREOF.	2,528.99	2.32 %
9	INORGANIC CHEMICALS; ORGANIC OR INORGANIC COMPOUNDS OF PRECIOUS METALS, OF RARE-EARTH METALS, OR RAD. ELEM. OR OF ISOTOPES.	1,607.48	1.47 %
10	PROJECT GOODS; SOME SPECIAL USES.	1,606.48	1.47 %
	INDIA'S TOTAL	1,09,116.07	

Source: Calculations based on the data from website <http://commerce.nic.in/eidb/default.asp>

Table-8
Top Commodities Imported from China in 2014-15

S.No	Product [H.S. code 2-Digit]	Amount in Rs Crore	Percentage (%) of India's total import from China
1	ELECTRICAL MACHINERY AND EQUIPMENT AND PARTS THEREOF; SOUND RECORDERS AND REPRODUCERS, TELEVISION IMAGE AND SOUND RECORDERS AND REPRODUCERS, AND PARTS.	1,02,361.43	27.70 %
2	NUCLEAR REACTORS, BOILERS, MACHINERY AND MECHANICAL APPLIANCES; PARTS THEREOF.	62,081.93	16.80 %
3	ORGANIC CHEMICALS	38,636.25	10.45 %
4	FERTILISERS.	19,375.26	5.24 %
5	IRON AND STEEL	16,630.61	4.50 %
6	PLASTIC AND ARTICLES THEREOF.	10,435.66	2.82 %
7	PROJECT GOODS; SOME SPECIAL USES.	8,879.82	2.40 %
8	ARTICLES OF IRON OR STEEL	8,504.90	2.30 %
9	NATURAL OR CULTURED PEARLS, PRECIOUS OR SEMIPRECIOUS STONES, PRE-METALS, CLAD WITH PRE-METAL AND ARTICLES THEREOF; IMITATION JEWELRY; COIN.	7,477.67	2.02 %
10	OPTICAL, PHOTOGRAPHIC CINEMATOGRAPHIC MEASURING, CHECKING PRECISION, MEDICAL OR SURGICAL INST. AND APPARATUS PARTS AND ACCESSORIES THEREOF;	7,467.55	2.02 %
INDIA'S TOTAL		3,69,565.36	

Source: Calculations based on the data from website <http://commerce.nic.in/eidb/default.asp>

The above three tables 6, 7, and 8 of composition of Import from China reveals the following points:

- In 2000-01, Mineral fuels & others was on top of commodity which was imported from China. In the later years Mineral fuels can not maintained its top position and even gone out from top commodity list in 2014-15. In 2000-01, Organic chemicals was on second position in top commodity list of import from China. It maintained its second position in 2007-08. It shifted to third position in 2014-15. Almost similar happened in the case of Nuclear reactors & others.
- In 2000-01, Electrical machinery & others was on fourth position of top commodity list of import from China. In later years it improved its position and come to first position in 2007-08 and 2014-15. Iron and steel was not in the top commodity list in 2000-01 but its

presence is noted in top list of commodities imported from China, in later years of study period. India was importing Silk from China in 2000-01 but it was gone out of top commodity list in 2007-08 and 2014-15.

India's Merchandise Trade with China: Composition of Export

Table-9
Top commodities exported to China in 2000-2001

S.No	Product [H.S. code 2-Digit]	Amount in Rs Crore	Percentage (%) of India's total export to China
1	ORES, SLAG AND ASH.	709.58	18.68 %
2	FISH AND CRUSTACEANS, MOLLUSCS AND OTHER AQUATIC INVERTEBRATES.	528.95	13.93 %
3	ORGANIC CHEMICALS	493.83	13.00 %
4	PLASTIC AND ARTICLES THEREOF.	369.90	9.74 %
5	COTTON.	321.67	8.47 %
6	SALT; SULPHUR; EARTHS AND STONE; PLASTERING MATERIALS, LIME AND CEMENT.	219.08	5.77 %
7	IRON AND STEEL	125.12	3.29 %
8	PHARMACEUTICAL PRODUCTS	82.36	2.17 %
9	PREPARED FEATHERS AND DOWN AND ARTICLES MADE OF FEATHERS OR OF DOWN; ARTIFICIAL FLOWERS; ARTICLES OF HUMAN HAIR.	81.17	2.14 %
10	NUCLEAR REACTORS, BOILERS, MACHINERY AND MECHANICAL APPLIANCES; PARTS THEREOF.	80.23	2.11 %
INDIA'S TOTAL		3,79,775.76	

Source: Calculations based on the data from website <http://commerce.nic.in/eidb/default.asp>

Table-10

Top commodities exported to China in 2007-08			
S.No	Product [H.S. code 2-Digit]	Amount in Rs Crore	Percentage (%) of India's total export to China
1	ORES, SLAG AND ASH.	24,797.86	56.88 %
2	COTTON.	4,350.05	9.98 %
3	ORGANIC CHEMICALS	2,518.59	5.78 %
4	COPPER AND ARTICLES THEREOF.	1,618.20	3.71 %
5	NUCLEAR REACTORS, BOILERS, MACHINERY AND MECHANICAL APPLIANCES; PARTS THEREOF.	940.08	2.16 %
6	PLASTIC AND ARTICLES THEREOF.	927.71	2.13 %
7	IRON AND STEEL	899.71	2.06 %
8	SALT; SULPHUR; EARTHS AND STONE; PLASTERING MATERIALS, LIME AND CEMENT.	808.27	1.85 %
9	MINERAL FUELS, MINERAL OILS AND PRODUCTS OF THEIR DISTILLATION; BITUMINOUS SUBSTANCES; MINERAL WAXES.	659.22	1.51 %
10	INORGANIC CHEMICALS; ORGANIC OR INORGANIC COMPOUNDS OF PRECIOUS METALS, OF RARE-EARTH METALS, OR RADI. ELEM. OR OF ISOTOPES.	632.04	1.45 %
	INDIA'S TOTAL	43,597.42	

Source: Calculations based on the data from website <http://commerce.nic.in/cidb/default.asp>

Table-11

Top Commodities Exported to China in 2014-15			
S.No	Product [H.S. code 2-Digit]	Amount in Rs Crore	Percentage (%) of India's total export to China
1	COTTON.	13,959.43	19 %
2	COPPER AND ARTICLES THEREOF.	11,562.91	16 %
3	MINERAL FUELS, MINERAL OILS AND PRODUCTS OF THEIR DISTILLATION; BITUMINOUS SUBSTANCES; MINERAL WAXES.	7,879.95	11 %
4	ORGANIC CHEMICALS	6,401.47	9 %
5	SALT; SULPHUR; EARTHS AND STONE; PLASTERING MATERIALS, LIME AND CEMENT.	3,799.60	5 %
6	ORES, SLAG AND ASH.	3,116.52	4 %
7	NUCLEAR REACTORS, BOILERS, MACHINERY AND MECHANICAL APPLIANCES; PARTS THEREOF.	3,055.05	4 %
8	PLASTIC AND ARTICLES THEREOF.	2,173.50	3 %
9	ELECTRICAL MACHINERY AND EQUIPMENT AND PARTS THEREOF; SOUND RECORDERS AND REPRODUCERS, TELEVISION IMAGE AND SOUND RECORDERS AND REPRODUCERS, AND PARTS.	1,712.24	2 %
10	ANIMAL OR VEGETABLE FATS AND OILS AND THEIR CLEAVAGE PRODUCTS; PRE-EDIBLE FATS; ANIMAL OR VEGETABLE WAXES.	1,667.76	2 %
INDIA'S TOTAL		73,030.43	

Source: Calculations based on the data from website <http://commerce.nic.in/eidb/default.asp>

The above three tables 9, 10, and 11 of composition of Export to China reveals the following points:

- India exports Ores, slag and ash in substantial value to China. Hence Ores, slag and ash maintained its presence in list of top exporting commodities in all the three years taken in consideration above.
- Fish & other was on the second position in the top commodities list. It gone out of list in 2007-08 and 2014-15.
- Organic chemicals maintained to be in top commodities list in all the three years taken in consideration above.
- Cotton shown a substantial improvement and finally attain first position in 2014-15 in the top commodity list of export to China.
- Copper & others as a new entry in 2007-08 got fourth position and thereafter second position in 2014-15 in top commodity list of export to China.

- Mineral fuels & others as a new entry in 2007-08 got ninth position and thereafter third position in 2014-15 in top commodity list of export to China.

CONCLUSION:

The above analysis may be concluded that, trade relations between India and China are attaining strength year by year. India's merchandise exports to and import from China rose tremendously since 2000-01. The value of India's merchandise exports to China were merely just Rs 3,797.76 crore in 2000-01 which shoot up by approximately 20 times and reached to Rs 73,030.43 crore in 2014-15. Although there was wide fluctuations in the growth rate.

The value of India's merchandise import from China were Rs 6,862.70 crore 2000-01 which shoot up by 54 times and reached to Rs 3,69,565.36 crore in 2014-15. Growth of India and China trade is remarkable. India faces massive trade imbalance heavily in favour of China.

A peak bilateral trade deficit is Rs -2, 96,534.93 crore in 2014-2015.

India mainly import secondary commodities from China. The major commodities imported from China to India are: Electrical Machineries, Mechanical machineries, Organic Chemicals, Fertilizers, Iron and Steel, Plastic & plastic related others items, Articles of Iron & Steel, Natural or cultured pearls, Surgical instruments.

India mainly exports primary commodities to China. The major commodities exported from India to China are: Cotton, Copper & copper articles, Mineral fuels, Organic chemicals, Salt & related commodities, Ores, Machinery & others commodities, Plastic & plastic related other commodities, Electrical Machineries, Vegetable fats etc.

LIMITATIONS: This research paper is mainly based on secondary data only, taken from website of Department of Commerce, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India.

This research paper will be helpful to those who are interested in India and China trade relations and will be a base for future researches on India and China trade relations.

SCOPE FOR FUTURE WORK: This research paper will be helpful to those who are interested in India and China trade relations and will be a base for future researches on India and China trade relations.

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